

Paged Skip List

Abstract

In memory sorted key-value collections are widely used as a programming technique. In this article we propose a new **Paged Skip List** collection which is suitable for large concurrently changed collections.

We'll discuss the pros. and cons. of existing sorted key-value collections and the new proposed **Paged Skip List** and we will show that **Paged Skip List** in many cases has much better performance, despite the more complex implementation.

Common definitions and notes

1. **K** - type of key
2. **V** - type of value
3. **[K,V]** - pair of key-value. Sometimes we'll call it **entry**
4. **Iterator<[K,V]>** - an object that provides a way to access the elements of a collection (subcollection) sequentially (one by one). In most cases it contains two methods:
 - **init()** - initialization of the iterator
 - **[K,V] next()** which returns the **next element** or **null** if there are not more elements.
5. **Comparison function** - the function `int some_function(K key1, K key2)`. The function compares two keys **key1** and **key2** and returns integer:
 - **> 0**, if **key1 > key2**
 - **== 0**, if **key1 == key2**
 - **< 0**, if **key1 < key2**
6. **Binary search algorithm** - see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binary_search_algorithm. For an array of N elements the average performance is $O(\log N)$ and count of the keys comparison is about $\log_2 N$
7. **Binary search function** - the function `int bsearch(entries_array, int fromIndex, int toIndex, K key, comparison_function)`. Where:
 - **entries_array** - array of **key-value** pairs **[K,V]**
 - **fromIndex** - the index of the first element (inclusive) to be searched
 - **toIndex** - the index of the last element (exclusive) to be searched
 - **key** - the value to be searched for

- **comparison_function** - [see #5](#)
 - **Return value** - index of the search key, if it is contained in the array within the specified range; otherwise, **-(insertion point) - 1**. The **insertion point** is defined as the point at which the key would be inserted into the array.
8. **Comparison relation** - one of (<, <=, ==, >, >=)
 9. **Hash map (hash table)** - mapping key to value using hash function. See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hash_table

Basic features of sorted key-value collections

For given two keys **K1** and **K2**, the collection can compare them – see [Comparison function](#).

1. Get by key **[K,V] findEntry(K key)**: returns pair **[K,V]** or **null** if absent.
2. Get closest **entry** by **Comparison relation (<, <=, ==, >, >=)** for given key: **[K,V] getClosestEntry(K key, Relation relation)**. Sometimes convenient versions **[K,V] getNext(K key)** and **[K,V] getPrevious(K key)** can be used.
3. **Read/write collection** (optional):
 1. **Insert, update, put** (insert if absent or update if exists), **delete** by key
 2. Optional: **putAll, deleteAll, deleteByRange**
4. **Concurrent collections** (optional): The collection should support all read and write operations (including iterators) from different threads with minimal whole collection locking. [Compare-and-swap](#) is preferred if possible.
5. **Swapped collection** (optional): Ability to swap portions of collection data with persistent storage. To save the memory we can store infrequently accessed portions of data in persistent storage and retrieve them as necessary. Possible usage of this kind of collection is a database cache.

Common Example

Let's suppose our collection contains chat messages from different users. The key of the message consists of two fields: **user id** and a **timestamp** in milliseconds (in format yyyy.HH.mm.ss.SSS) and sorted by this key as string. E.g. for user **aaa**: the key **aaa/2024.03.14.12.38.12.126**.

1. In most cases the new inserted message will have the max timestamp. So, the inserted key will be placed at the end of all messages for the specific user.

2. The application frequently needs to retrieve the last page of chat messages (e.g. last 20 messages) for a specific user from a collection
 3. When the user scrolls a list of messages, the application doesn't need the exact position. Something like goto 25% from the beginning will be ok
-

Possible optimization features

1. **Hotspots.** See [common example](#). In this case the entry (maybe virtual) with the key **aaaa/9999** (suppose the all messages year will be less than 9999) will be the max key for **aaa** user and we'll call it a **hotspot**. The most application data is processed close to the hotspot key – In our [example](#) insert message and read last page are processed close to **aaaa/999**. Certainly, we can implement this behavior without optimization for **hotspots**. However, we have the opportunity to enhance performance if the collection supports hotspot optimization. Possible methods to add:
 - a. register/unregister hotspot: **register(K hotspotKey)** and **unregister(K hotspotKey)**
 - b. Options:
 - i. To all access methods add parameter **hotspotKey**. E.g. **[K,V] findEntry(K key, K hotspotKey)**.
 - ii. More clear option: add method **HotspotView getView(K hotspotKey)** where **HotspotView** has the same methods as a general collection and **HotspotView** implementation will contain the optimisations for **hotspotKey**.
2. **Hot subcollection.** See [common example](#). Suppose the application accesses data for the specific user **aaa** in a specific application workflow. That means instead of accessing data from the whole collection we can use narrowed collection between keys **aaa/** and **aaa/9999**. This can be a subject for performance optimizations. Possible methods to add :
 - a. register/unregister hot subcollection: **SubCollectionId registerHotSubcollection(K keyStart, K keyEnd)** and **unregisterHotSubcollection(SubCollectionId subCollectionId)**
 - b. Options:
 - i. add to all access methods parameter **SubCollectionId**. E.g. **[K,V] findEntry(K key, SubCollectionId subCollectionId)**
 - ii. [Same idea as for hotspot](#): add method **HotspotView getView(SubCollectionId subCollectionId)** where **HotspotView** has the same methods as a general collection and **HotspotView** implementation will contain the optimisations for **Hot subcollection**

3. **Forward Iterators.** Iterate forward (in ascending sort order) through all keys between given keys in ascending order: **Iterator<[K,V]> forwardIterator(K startKey, K endKey)**. Certainly forward iteration can be implemented using a loop of **[K,V] getAfter(K key)**, but internal collection implementation may be significantly faster than the “getAfter” loop.
4. **Backward Iterators.** Iterate backward (in descending sort order) through all keys between given keys : **Iterator<[K,V]> backwardIterator(K startKey, K endKey)**. Same as for forward iterator internal collection implementation maybe significantly faster.
5. **Calculate distance.** **Int distance(K startKey, K endKey)**. Certainly a distance can be implemented using a loop of “getAfter”. In most cases internal collection implementation may be significantly faster than the “getAfter” loop.
6. **Jump.** **[K,V] jump(K startKey, int count)**. This is like an “inverse function” for **distance**: it finds the entry with which the distance **between** startKey and found entry equals the specified count. Same as for **distance()**, internal collection implementation may be significantly faster than the “getAfter” loop.
7. **Approx distance and approx jump.** See [common example #3](#).

Sorted collection implementations

Sorted Array

Sorted Array is a flat array of **entries** sorted by **key**. Array has a fixed number of elements (array length) and it has a very fast method **getByOffset(int offset)** where **offset 0 <= offset < length**

Basic features implementation:

1. [findEntry](#) and [getClosestEntry](#) may be implemented using [Binary search algorithm](#).
2. [Insert and delete](#) entry by key. The implementation should shift the array. This is very slow operation $O(N)$

3. [Concurrent collections](#). Implementation of concurrent changes without locking the whole collection is very complex. The main problem is shifting of the array which changes many array elements. One insert or delete can change on average half of the elements so we need to lock a big part of the array.
4. [Swap](#). Implementation of swap is quite complex too. There are two problems: 1. Removing/restoring a big part of the sorted array ([see #3](#)), 2. We need support for additional structure for swapped parts of the array (e.g. **start key, end key, element count**) and use it for e.g. the [binary search](#) algorithm.

Possible optimization features:

1. [Hotspots](#). Implementation of **hotspots** is quite simple. We can use **hash map (hash table)** for mapping hotspot **keys** to array **offsets**. The initial value of offset is **-1** (it is applied in the hotspot registration process). If the **offset** corresponds to the correct entry, you'll use it. Otherwise, you'll recalculate the offset using a [binary search](#) (bsearch) function.

The performance of **getLast()** function without **hotspot** is $O(\log N)$ and with **hotspot**: $O(1)$.

2. [Hot subcollection](#). The Idea of implementation of this feature is very close to hotspot one. We can use **hot_collection_map** (hash map) with key **subCollectionId** and the value which contains two pairs [**startKey, startOffset**] and [**endKey, endKeyOffset**].

Suppose the collection of **common example** contains **m** users and average **n** entries per user. The average comparison count of **findEntry()** function without **hot subcollection** will be $\log_2(n * m) = \log_2 n + \log_2 m$. And with **hot subcollection** $\log_2 n$ only.

3. [Forward Iterators](#). The implementation is quite simple:
 - a. Read only collections:

```

{
    int startOffset;
    int endOffset;
    int currentOffset;

    init(K startKey, K endKey)
    {
        startOffset = calculate_offset(startKey)
        endOffset = calculate_offset(endKey)
    }
  
```

```

        currentOffset = startOffset - 1
    }
    [K,V] next()
    {
        currentOffset = currentOffset + 1;
        if(currentOffset >= endOffset) return null;

        return array.getByOffset(currentOffset)
    }
}

```

The number of key comparisons will be $2\log_2 N$ only (for finding offsets of **startKey** and **endKey**). The **next()** method doesn't contain key comparisons at all!!

b. Read - write collections.

Unlike the read only version we cannot use **endOffset** – it may be changed. So we should check the returned value of **next()** and if the value \geq **endKey** - return null.

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N + L$ - where L is the count of the **next()** function invoked.

4. [Backward Iterators](#). The implementation is quite close for **Forward Iterators**. The main differences: need start iteration from **endKey**, $\text{currentOffset} = \text{currentOffset} - 1$ and for end of iteration check **startKey**.
5. [Calculate distance](#). The implementation is simple: find offsets for **startKey** and **endKey** and return **endOffset - startOffset**. The number of key comparisons will be $2\log_2 N$.
6. [Jump](#). The implementation is simple: find offset for **startKey** and return **array.getByOffset(startOffset + count)**
7. [Approx distance and approx jump](#). The accurate **distance** and **jump** works fast. So, no reason to implement **approx** versions.

Conclusions of Sorted array

Pros:

1. Quite simple implementation
2. Fast for: read only and/or rare changed and/or small (not more than tens of entries) collections

Cons.:

1. Very slow change implementation
2. Almost impossible to implement concurrent changes without lock of the whole collection
3. Swapping a portion of the collection is too complex.

Skip List

Skip list (or **skiplist**) is a probabilistic sorted data structure (sorted collection) that allows read/write operations with performance $O(\log n)$. See [Skip list - Wikipedia](#). The main advantage of **skiplist** is that all changes (write) operations use a small number of internal nodes. So, effective concurrent implementation is possible.

We are not going to discuss read-only of **skiplist** – certainly, the read-only version of a **skiplist** is more complex and with worse performance compared to a **sorted array**.

We are not going to discuss implementations based on special language features like Java's WeakReference – some algorithms can be implemented using these features. Instead, we can focus on more general algorithms that are widely applicable and independent of language-specific features or optimizations.

Implementations of all methods (especially concurrent implementation) are quite complex. We are going to explain the main ideas only.

Basic features implementation:

1. [findEntry](#) and [getClosestEntry](#) may be implemented using a recursive algorithm (quote from Wikipedia):
A search for a target element begins at the head element in the top list, and proceeds horizontally until the current element is greater than or equal to the target. If the current element is equal to the target, it has been found. If the current element is greater than the target, or the search reaches the end of the linked list, the procedure is repeated after returning to the previous element and dropping down vertically to the next lower list.
2. [Insert and Delete](#). Implementations:
 1. **Insert** implementation: find the insertion point and insert to appropriate layers linked lists. Layers to insert can be obtain using generation random value (probability)

2. **Delete** implementation: find the node and exclude it from all layers linked lists.

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N$.

3. **Concurrent collections**. Skiplist is suitable for concurrent changes implementation.
4. **Swap**. Implementation of swap is quite complex, but simpler than the corresponding implementation for **sorted array**. There are two problems: 1. Removing/restoring a big part of the **skiplist**, 2. We need support for additional structure for swapped parts of the collection (e.g. **start key, end key**) and use it for e.g. the **binary search** algorithm.

Possible optimization features:

1. **Hotspots**. **Skiplist** doesn't have offsets. So, unlike **Sorted list** implementation based on **hashtable** which maps **hotspot keys** to offsets, we don't have a good idea for a **hotspot** implementation of **skiplist**.
2. **Hot subcollection**. Same problem as for **hotspots**. No implementation.
3. **Forward Iterators**. The implementation is quite simple – every data entry of a **skiplist** has a reference to the next entry. Algorithm:
 - a. In the **init()** method initialize the **currentEntry** variable with a result of finding the start entry by **startKey**.
 - b. In the **next()**: if returned **entry.key** \geq **endKey** return **null** otherwise keep **currentEntry** in **temp** variable, **currentEntry = currentEntry.next** and **return temp**.

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N + L$ - where L is the count of the **next()** function invoked.

4. **Backward Iterators**. In contrast to **Forward Iterators** we should implement **backward Iterators** using generic **getPrevious(K key)**. The reason: **skiplist** data entry doesn't contain reference to a previous **entry**.
The number of key comparisons will be $L * \log_2 N$ - where L is the count of the **next()** function invoked. Very slow!
5. **Calculate distance**. The implementation: create **Iterator<K> forwardIterator(K startKey, K endKey)** and count all **next()** invocations. So, the performance will

be close to the **forward iterator**. The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N + L$ - where L is a distance. Quite slow for big L values.

6. **Jump**. There are two variants for **jump** implementation: **forward jump** (implemented using **forward iterator**) and **backward jump** (**backward iterator**). See performance calculations for appropriate iterators.
7. **Approx distance and approx jump**. The implementation idea: calculate the distance on high levels (not data levels). E.g. iteration on the first layer passes $p * L$ entries. Where p is a probability of the first layer entry and L is a "real" distance. In case $p = 0.5$ the **approx distance** comparison count will be $\log_2 N + L/2$.

Conclusions of Skip list

One of the main advantages of **skiplists** is their suitability for concurrent implementations. The performance for **findEntry**, **getClosest**, **insert**, **delete** is about $O(\log_2 N)$. The **Forward iterators** are quite fast. Implementations of other **possible optimization features** are slow or almost impossible (see [## 4,5,6,7](#) of the previous chapter).

Paged skip list (PSL)

Paged skip list is a new suggested sorted collection.

The idea of **PSL** is quite close to the traditional **skiplist** with “[PSL pages](#)” instead of **skiplist entries**.

PSL has main properties:

1. [Comparison function](#)
2. **Global min key**: all Collection keys are strongly greater than **global min key**
3. **Global max key**: all Collection keys are strongly less than **global max key**
4. **Average page size**

Note: in most use cases values of **Global min/max** keys are quite obvious.

PSL Page

The **PSL Page** is a small set of entries (max hundred entries). Entry is a **key - value pair**: **Entry.key** and **Entry.value**.

To simplify the explanation, let's imagine that a **PSL Page** is a small sorted by **key** array (see [sorted arrays](#) chapter of this article).

Every **PSL Page** has properties:

1. **Page min key**: all page keys are strongly less than **Page min key**
2. **Page max key**: all page keys are less or equal than **Page max key**
3. **Page type**: one of **Data page** or **Index page**. **Data page** contains a sorted set of pairs: **[K, V]** and **Index page**: contains a sorted set of pairs: **[reference key, reference to another page]**. Where the **reference to another page** is clear and the **reference key** is a **Page max key** of the referenced page.
4. May be additional properties like: **isSwapped**

EntryId

An object with type **EntryId** is an additional key of **entry** in the **page**. By its value we can get the **entry** from the **page**. We assume that accessing the **entry** by **EntryId** will be much faster than accessing by **entry key**.

1. **entryId** belongs to the **PSL page** it was created on.

2. The **EntryId** may be not stable – may be changed when adding/removing **entry** to/from the **page** and **splitting** the **page**. The **PSL page** has a method for checking validity of **entryId**. The stability of **entryId** is very important for good performance: changing the **EntryId** frequently can reduce performance.
3. Comparison of two valid **entryIds** return the same result as comparison of appropriate **entry keys** and may be faster than key comparisons.

For **sorted array** implementation **entryId** may be the array offset.

PSL Page main methods:

1. **[EntryId, Entry] getById(EntryId entryId)**: It should be a fast method.
2. **Boolean isValid(EntryId entryId, K key)**: checks if the **entryId** belongs to this page and points to entry with the same key.
3. **[EntryId, Entry] findByKey(K key)**: it returns the pair **[EntryId, Entry]** where **Entry.key** closest key \leq **key** parameter. Sorted array implementation can use **binary search**.
4. **[EntryId, Entry] getNext(EntryId entryId)**: May return **EOP** (end of page). Sorted array implementation will return the pair with array offset equals **entryId + 1**.
5. **[EntryId, Entry] getPrevious(EntryId entryId)**: May return **EOP** (end of page). Sorted array implementation will return the pair with array offset equals **entryId - 1**.
6. **Int size()**: returns entry count.
7. **[EntryId, Entry] getFirst()**: returns the first page entry. Sorted array implementation will return the pair with array offset **0**.
8. **[EntryId, Entry] getLast()**: returns the last entry. Sorted array implementation will return the pair with array offset **size() - 1**.
9. **Insert, put, delete** entry by **EntryId**
10. **new_pages[] splitPage()**: returns array of new **pages** – a result of split this page. The **Page min key** of the first element should be equal to the **Page min key** of this page. The **Page max key** of the last element should be equal to the

Page max key of this page. We need this method for “breaking up” too long pages. Note: It is better to calculate split points using probabilistic algorithms

Let’s call **Entry Coordinate** the pair **[EntryId, Entry.key]**

In **Picture 1** (below) you can see an example of the **PSL**.

Picture 1

Note.

1. All keys of all pages on the same level are unique.
2. All page ranges of keys at the same level are not intersect. In other words: for pages *i* and *j* ranges **[min key i, max key i]** and **[min key j, max key j]** are not intersect.

Level (data) 0 is the lowest level pages. We call them **data pages**. Every **page** contains **key - value entries** sorted by **key**.

Level (index) 1 consists of **Index pages**. Every page contains **[reference key (max key of the level 0 page), reference to level 0 page]** sorted by **key**.

Level (index) K consists of **Index pages**. Every page contains **[reference key (max key of the level K-1 page), reference to level K-1 page]** sorted by **key**.

The **root level** (see picture 1) contains only one page - we'll call it the **root page**.

Min key of all pages of the same level will be the **Global min key** of **PSL**.

Max key of all pages of the same level will be the **Global max key** of **PSL**.

The newly created PSL collection: the collection contains the single **level 0 (data)** which contains a single empty page with **Min key** equals to **Global min key** and **Max key** equals to **Global max key**.

Find entry by **key** algorithm

1. Start from the [root page](#) (single page). **currPage = root_page**
2. In **currPage** find the closest entry with **key >= key** using **findByKey**.
3. If the **currPage** is a [data page](#), return **currPage** and finish the algorithm.
Otherwise, **currPage = currPage.reference_to_next_level_page** and **goto #2**

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N$.

Entry path

Let's suppose during the find entry algorithm we collect pairs **[level, Entry coordinate]**. Let's sort collected pairs by **level** descending. The result will be an array named **Entry path**.

E.g. array: **[level: 2,[key: aaa/999,entryId: 8]]**; **[level: 1,[key: aaa/777, entryId: 3]]**;
[level:0,[key: aaa/111, entryId: 5]]; **Level 2** is the **root page**.

Let's suppose we stored this [entry path](#) and sometimes later we want to find the entry with **key = aaa/111**. We can use the stored **entry path**.

The algorithm idea is quite simple.

Start from the 0-th **path element**, get **page (root page)** -> find **page entry** by **entryId** -> check **entry key** (should be equal to appropriate **entry key** of **entry path element**). If the check fails, recreate the **entry path** from this **path element**. If the check passes, get **page** from **page reference** and continue with the next **entry path** element, till the end of **entry path** elements.

Insert [K, V] entry algorithm

Suppose the entry for insert has a key: **KEY**.

Find the **data page** which contains a **page entry** with **entry key** closest and $> \text{KEY}$. By the way, collect pairs: **found pages** and **entryIds** (same as we do this in **find entry by key** algorithm).

Insert the entry to the just found **data page**. Check if the **data page** contains too many entries. If the check is failed \rightarrow finish the algorithm. If the check is passed, split the **page** and insert new **page entries** to the **previous page** from the **found pages**. Check the just changed **page** if a **split** is needed. If so, split and insert **page entries** to the **previous page** from the **found pages**. If not - finish the algorithm. Etc...The new **root level** may be created.

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N$.

The total time of **insert** depends on **insert** into **page** and number of **splits**. For a big **average page size**, **insert** into **page** may take more time and **split** will be quite rare. For small **average page size**, **insert** into **page** may take less time and **split** will be quite often.

Delete entry by key

Suppose the key for delete: **KEY**

Find the **data page** which contains a **page entry** with **entry key** $== \text{KEY}$ and delete it.

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N$.

Basic features implementation:

1. **findEntry** and **getClosestEntry**: see [find entry by key algorithm](#). The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N$.
2. **Insert** and **Delete**. See [Insert \[K, V\] entry algorithm](#) and [Delete entry by key](#)

3. **Concurrent collections.** PSL is suitable for concurrent implementations – the change algorithms use a small number of **pages**.
4. **Swap.** We can implement swap/uswap for pages: the **isSwapped** flag can be added. When needed, write to swap storage, remove all **entries** from the **page** and set **isSwapped** to true. To restore (unswap) read all entries from swap storage, add them to the **page** and set **isSwapped** to false. **Swap** is not so reasonable for a small **average page size**.

Possible optimization features:

1. **Hotspots.** Implementation based on **hashtable** which maps **hotspot keys** to the **entry path** and use [find entry by path algorithm](#). The performance of using **hotspots** depends on **PSL page** implementation: stability of **entryId** value. Anyway, comparison number: best case $\log_{\text{average page size}} N$ and worst case $\log_2 N$.
2. **Hot subcollections.** Implementation based on **hashtable** which maps **subCollectionId** to pair [**entry_path_of_startKey, entry_path_of_endKey**]. The performance of **hot subcollections** (same as **hotspots**) depends on stability of **entryId** value.
3. **Forward Iterators.** Implementation idea:

In **init()** method implementation find the data page which contains **startKey**. By the way, collect pairs: found pages and **entryIds** (same as we do this in [find entry by key algorithm](#)), sort it by **PSL level** and keep the collected pairs array in instance variable **collected_pairs_array**.

next() method implementation:

```
new_entry_and_entryId =  
collected_pairs_array[0].page.getNext(collected_pairs_array[0].entryId);
```

If **new_entry_and_entryId** equals **EOP**, try to get the next **data page** (simple recursive algorithm: go up to **level 1 page (collected_pairs_array[1])**, **result = getNext(collected_pairs_array[1].entryId)**. If the **result** does not equals **EOP**, **collected_pairs_array[0] = result**. Otherwise, go up to **level 2 page** etc.).

If `new_entry_and_entryId` still equals `EOP`, then the iterator `next()` will return `null`, otherwise iterator `next()` will return `collected_pairs_array[0].page.getByld(collected_pairs_array[0].entryId)`;

Of course, before returning the `next()` result we should check it with the iterator `endKey` value and return `null` if the result \geq `endKey`. This checking can be excluded if `page maxKey` property \geq `endKey`.

The number of key comparisons will be $\log_2 N$ for the `init()` and `0` or `1` for `next()`.

4. [Backward iterators](#). The implementation idea is similar to **Forward Iterators**. Same performance considerations.
5. [Calculate distance](#). Implementation idea:
Start page iteration from the **data page** which contains `startKey` – similar to page iteration in **forward iterator**. Calculate the **result**: the initial value is `0` and for every page add:
 1. If the page contains **startKey (start page)**, iterate into this page from `startKey` till `EOP` and calculate iteration count.
 2. If the page contains **endKey (end page)**, iterate from first entry to `endKey` and calculate iteration count.
 3. For 'intermediate' page take `size()` of page

The number of key comparisons will be about $\log_2 N + (\text{average page size})/2$.

6. [Jump](#). The implementation idea is similar to [Calculate distance](#) with the same performance considerations.
7. [Approx distance and approx jump](#).
 - a. **Approx distance**. The implementation may be similar to the accurate ones with difference: ignore interactions in `startPage/endPage` take for calculation the `(start page.size() + endPage.size())/2`.
 - b. **approx jump**. Implementation idea: take in account full pages only.

The number of key comparisons will be about $\log_2 N$

PSL page implementations

Implementation requirements of PSL page:

1. **Good performance of `findByKey()`.**

2. **Good performance** of `insert()` and `delete()`
3. **Performance of access methods by EntryId** (e.g. `getById()`, `getNext()`, `getPrevious()`): should be much better than `findByKey()`.
4. **Fast `size()`**.
5. **Stability of EntryId**. Very important.
6. **Small additional space**. Preferable.
7. **Concurrent changes**. In most cases (except may be **split page**) with minimal lock of the whole page.

Let's discuss the [average page size](#) property of the **PSL** collection:

1. Too small (e.g. 2 - 16) :
 - a. Advantage: ability to use more simple implementation (e.g. **sorted array**)
 - b. Disadvantage: frequent **split** page and as a result: average complexity of **insert** grows, not stable **EntryId**, **PSL** levels grows too.
2. For bigger **average page size** (64 - 512 or more): need to find a good implementation (may be more complex).

Sorted array implementation

For **sorted arrays PSL page** implementation we can use array offset as an **EntryId**.

Requirements:

1. **Good performance** of `findByKey()`. $O(\log N)$ - looks **OK**.
2. **Good performance** of `insert()` and `delete()`. **Not so good** – because of shifting the tail of the array. May be OK for small **average page size**.
3. **Performance of access methods by EntryId**. **OK** (simple and fast implementation)
4. **Fast `size()`**. **OK**.
5. **Stability of EntryId**. **Not stable** – because of shifting the tail of the array.
6. **Small additional space**. **OK**
7. **Concurrent changes**. **Almost impossible** – because of shifting the tail of the array.

Sorted array implementation can be used for **pages** with small **average page size** and/or for rarely changed **pages** (e.g. for high level **PSL pages**).

Skiplist implementation

For **skiplist** implementation there is no good/native **EntryId** implementation. So, we can use the **key** as the **EntryId**.

Requirements:

1. **Good performance of findByKey().** $O(\log N)$ - looks **OK**.
2. **Good performance of insert() and delete().** **Not so good** – $O(\log N)$
3. **Performance of access methods by EntryId.** **Not so good** - for all methods $O(\log N)$ performance
4. **Fast size().** **OK**.
5. **Stability of EntryId.** **OK** - because **EntryId** is same as the **key**
6. **Small additional space.** **More or less OK.** $O(N)$
7. **Concurrent changes.** **OK**

The **Skiplist** implementation of **PSL pages** is quite slow and eliminates the most of advantages of **PSL collection**. In order to improve this implementation, a combination of **skiplist** and **hashtable** may be used.

Extended sorted array (ESA)

Suppose we have a fixed length array. Elements of this array may be a **null element** or a **key-value element** (see picture 2).

Picture 2.

All **key-value elements** should be sorted by **key**. The **null element** can be replaced with a **key-value element** (insert). A **key-value element** can be replaced by the **null element** (delete).

We need to make simple changes in the **binary search** algorithm: use the closest non **null element** for comparison.

We call **coordinate**: the integer, using it we can get the **element** from **ESA**. In our example on [Picture 2](#) the **coordinate** is equal to an **array offset**. Later we will see the cases where the **coordinate** will not be equal to an **array offset**

Internal method `[c1, c2] findCoordinates(K keyToFind)` where:

1. **c1** - the **coordinate** of the closest **key-value element** with the element key less or equal to the **keyToFind** or **-1** if not exist.
2. **c2** - the **coordinate** of the closest **key-value element** with the element key greater or equal to the **keyToFind** or **N** if not exist.

So, if the array contains the **key-value element** with key equals to **keyToFind** the **c1** will be equals to **c2**.

The **delete** algorithm is simple: **findCoordinates()** and if **c1 == c2**, replace **array[c1] = null**.

The **insert** or **put** algorithm are more tricky:

1. If **c2 - c1 == 0** then return duplicate for **insert** or replace **array[c1]** with new value for **put**.
2. If **c2 - c1 > 1** that means there is at least one **null element** between **c1** and **c2**. Use a random number between **c1 + 1** and **c2** and use it as **coordinate** for the new (inserted) element.
3. If **c2 - c1 == 1** that means there are no **null elements** between **c1** and **c2**.

Let's start the explanation with an example.

Suppose **c1 == 2** and **c2 == 3**. So we don't have **null elements** between these **coordinates**.

Let's add a new array (**Array1**) with the same length as source **Array0** (see [Picture 2](#)). We will call it an **additional array**. At the beginning all elements of **Array1** will be **null**. From now **coordinate** of all elements of the **Array0** will be **nc = 2 * c** (**multiplier** is 2). **Array0** will contain even elements and **Array1** will contain odd elements. If we need to get an element with **coordinate C**:

1. For even **C** -> **Array0[C/2]**
2. For odd **C** -> **Array1[(C - 1)/2]**

In this example the **coordinate** \neq **offset**.

Our "old" offsets were **c1 == 2** and **c2 == 3** and the new values will be **nc1 = 2*2 == 4** and **nc2 = 3*2 == 6**. (Note: the elements with the new offsets still have the same offsets in **Array0**). Now **nc2 - nc1 == 2**, so we can insert a new element with **c3 == 5**. Because **5** is odd we will put it to **Array1** with array offset $(5 - 1)/2 = 2$.

Logically, this behavior looks like we expanded the original array – we create a double-length new array and copy all elements from the original array to even offsets of the new array. The advantage of the explained approach: no copying is required at all.

In this example we use **multiplier = 2**. This is not necessary.

For **multiplier == 3**, **Array1** length will be twice greater than length of **Array0**. All new **nc = 3*c** for **Array0**. If we need to get an element with **coordinate C**: suppose **R** is a remainder of **c/3** (we will use **%** for remainder operation **R = c % 3**):

1. If **R == 0** -> **Array0[c/3]**
2. If **R > 0** -> **Array1[c-((c - R)/3 + 1)]**

More general: for some **multiplier = M** (where **M** is integer **M > 1**) and **Array1** length will be **M** times greater than length of **Array0**.

All new **nc = multiplier * c** for **Array0**. If we need to get an element with **coordinate C**: suppose **R = C % M**

1. If **R == 0** -> **Array0[C/M]**
2. If **R > 0** -> **Array1[C-((C - R)/M + 1)]**

It is possible to add a new **Array2 (multiplier = M2)** in addition to **Array1 (multiplier = M1)**. All new **nc = M1 * M2 * c** for **Array0**.

Picture 3.

More formal.

% - integer remainder operation **a % b = p**, where **p** is a remainder.

L - count of arrays

i - array index $0 \leq i < L$

A_i - i-th array. E.g. **Array0 = A₀**, **Array1 = A₁** etc.

$$\widehat{A}_L = \{A_0, A_1, \dots, A_{L-1}\}$$

m_i - multiplier of i-th array. m_0 is always 1.

$$\widehat{M}_L = \{m_0, m_1, \dots, m_{L-1}\}$$

$$M_i = \prod_{j=i}^L m_j$$

C_L - **coordinate** to find. Of course, its value depends of \widehat{M}_L

$$c_i = \frac{C_L}{M_i}$$

$$r_i = C_L \% m_i$$

Calculation of i :

$$i = \max_j (r_j) - \text{for } r_j \neq 0$$

Calculation K_i offset in A_i :

For $i > 0$

$$K_i = c_i - \left(\frac{c_i - r_i}{m_i} + 1 \right)$$

For $i = 0$

$$K_0 = c_0$$

Calculation C_L by K_i :

$$1. i = 0 \Rightarrow C_L = K_0 \cdot M_0$$

$$2. i > 0 \Rightarrow$$

For $m_i > 2$

$$\bar{r}_i = 1 + K_i \% (m_i - 1)$$

and for $m_i = 2$

$$\bar{r}_i = 1$$

$$C_L = \frac{m_i^{(K_i+1)} - \bar{r}_i}{m-1}$$

Full coordinate (FC)

FC is a pair $FC_L = \{C_L, \bar{M}_L\}$ - where $\bar{M}_L = \prod_{j=0}^{L-1} m_j$

Suppose we keep the **FC** and sometimes later we want to use it. The problem: arrays count can be changed. Let's assume the arrays count can only grow. So, $L_1 \geq L$. This assumption is quite obvious – we will never remove an array from the array

set \widehat{A}_L . So, $\widehat{M}_{L_1} = \widehat{M}_L \cup \{m_L, m_{L+1}, \dots, m_{L_1-1}\}$. We can recalculate C_{L_1} :

$$C_{L_1} = C_L \cdot \prod_{j=L}^{L_1-1} m_j$$

We can compare **FCs**:

Suppose we have FC_{L_1} and FC_{L_2} and $L_2 \geq L_1$.

$$K = \prod_{j=L_1}^{L_2} m_j$$

$$\widehat{C} = K \cdot C_{L_1}$$

And now we can compare \widehat{C} and C_{L_1} as integers.

FC - is stable (except **split**) – we always can calculate “real” **coordinate** from **FC** and we can get the same **entry** from **ESA** despite **ESA** changes. So, we can use **FC** as an **EntryId**.

Discussions

1. Of null entries for Array0

ESA may be created as a result:

- a. Creating the single page of the **Root Level** of **PSL**. In this case the **Array0** will contain only **null elements** and finding the closest **key-value element** (e.g for **insert()**) may take time to skip **null elements**. Using the **Root level** for **insert()** is quite rare, so skipping **null elements** will have a little impact on overall performance. On the other hand we can use the bitmap (array of bits) with 1 - for **key-value element** and 0 - for **null element** and implement skipping of **null elements** using bitwise operations - this will be much faster than simply looping over the elements.
- b. The result of **split()**. The **split()** algorithm creates two pages (more or less the same size) from the one page. In this case the newly created pages will have the same count of **null** and **key-value elements**. So, the loop over **null elements** will be little and will not impact performance.

2. **Of Array0 length**. We suggest **Array0** length will be **1.25 * (average page size)**.

3. **Of Arrays count (L)**. We don't expect too big **L**. Something about max 3 - 4

4. **Of additional (non Array0) arrays space**. Sometimes we will need to use a large value for the corresponding **multiplier** (See **common example** above). So,

the **additional array (e.g. Array1)** length will be too big, but in most cases only a small part of the array will be used (will contain **key-value elements**). We can decrease the used space using a **chunked array**: we can split the original array into fixed length **chunks** and allocate space for the specific **chunk** on demand.

5. **Of multipliers** value. Typically, the multiplier can be any integer value > 0 , but a power of 2 is much better - this can simplify the calculations.

Requirements:

1. **Good performance of findByKey().** OK. $O(\log N)$. See [c1, c2] findCoordinates(K keyToFind) above.
2. **Good performance of insert() and delete().** OK. $O(\log N)$
3. **Performance of access methods by EntryId.** OK (simple and fast implementation)
4. **Fast size().** OK.
5. **Stability of EntryId.** OK. Except split()
6. **Small additional space.** More or less OK. See discussion above.
7. **Concurrent changes.** OK. ESA is suitable for concurrent implementation.

Conclusions about Paged Skip List

The **Paged Skip List** with **Extended sorted array** although a more complex implementation, has advantages of **Sorted array** and **Skip list**.

Conclusions

In **Table 1** we've collected all attributes of each sorted key-value collection discussed above.

Features	Sorted Array	Skip List	Paged Skip List (with ESA)
<u>Basic features</u>			
1. Get by key [K,V] findEntry(K key)	OK O(log N)	OK O(log N)	OK O(log N)
2. Get closest entry	OK O(log N)	OK O(log N)	OK O(log N)
3. write operations	Bad. Insert and delete performance O(N)	OK O(log N)	OK O(log N)
4. Concurrent implementation	Impossible	Possible	Possible
5. Swap implementation	Impossible	Impossible	Possible
<u>Possible optimization features</u>			
1. Hotspots	OK	No implementation.	OK
2. Hot subcollection	OK	No implementation.	OK
3. Forward Iterators	OK	OK	OK
4. Backward Iterators	OK	Very slow	OK
5. Calculate distance	OK	Very slow for big distance values	OK
6. Jump	OK	Very slow for big distance values especially for jump back	OK
7. Approx distance and approx jump	OK	Slow for big distance values	OK
<u>Additional space</u>	Not need additional space	About 50%	Depends on average page size , but less than 50%
<u>Concurrent implementation complexity</u> (0 ÷ 100)	10	50	100

Table 1.

From the table you can see: **Paged Skip List** with **extended sorted array** as a **page** implementation seems to be preferable in most cases (albeit more complex implementation).